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3 **DRUGS OF ABUSE IN URBAN GROUNDWATER. A CASE STUDY:**
4 **BARCELONA.**

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36 **ABSTRACT**

37 This study is concerned with drugs of abuse (DAs) and their metabolites in
38 urban groundwater at field scale in relation to (1) the spatial distribution of DAs in
39 Barcelona's groundwater, (2) the depth of the groundwater samples, (3) the presence of
40 DAs in recharge sources, and (4) the assessment of the fate of DAs in Barcelona
41 aquifers. To this end, 37 urban groundwater samples were collected in the city of
42 Barcelona and a total of 21 drugs were analyzed including cocaine, amphetamine-like
43 compounds, opioids, lysergics and cannabinoids and the prescribed drugs
44 benzodiazepines. Overall, the highest groundwater concentrations (around 200 ng/L in
45 SAP-4) and the largest number of detected DAs were found in zones basically
46 recharged by a river that receives large amounts of effluents from waste water treatment
47 plants (WWTPs). In contrast, the urbanized areas yielded not only lower concentrations
48 but also a much smaller number of drugs, which suggests a local origin. In fact, cocaine
49 and its metabolite were dominant in more prosperous neighbourhoods, whereas the
50 cheaper MDMA was the dominant DA in poorer districts. Measured concentrations
51 were consistently smaller than those estimated from the waste water fraction in
52 groundwater samples, suggesting that DAs undergo removal processes in both reducing
53 and oxidizing conditions.

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56 **Key words: drugs of abuse, urban groundwater, mixing ratios, removal processes,**
57 **Barcelona.**

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70 1. INTRODUCTION

71 In recent years, drugs of abuse (DAs) and their metabolites have been
72 recognized as environmental contaminants. These compounds have become a major
73 cause for concern because of their occurrence and because their toxicity and persistence
74 are not well known. Despite being detected in low concentrations, DAs may produce
75 potentially harmful effects on ecosystems and human health (Jones-Lepp *et al.*, 2004,
76 Postigo *et al.*, 2008a). Moreover, the incomplete removal of some DAs during
77 conventional waste water treatment represents the main source in surface and ground
78 waters. Since both surface and ground waters can be used for water supply purposes,
79 DAs and their metabolites have become a matter of considerable concern.

80 Numerous studies have reported the occurrence of DAs in the environment. The
81 first comprehensive work was carried out by Zuccato *et al.*, (2005) in Italy. These
82 authors described the presence of the illicit drug cocaine and its metabolite
83 benzoylecgonine in wastewaters and surface waters. They applied at a local level the
84 sewage epidemiological approach (Daughton, 2001) employing the measurements of
85 benzoylecgonine in sewage water to estimate collective cocaine usage. Since then, a
86 number of research groups have applied this methodology all around Europe, e.g. in
87 Belgium (Van Nuijs *et al.*, 2011), France (Karolak *et al.*, 2010), Ireland (Bones *et al.*,
88 2007), Croatia (Terzic *et al.*, 2010), Italy (Mari *et al.*, 2009, Zuccato *et al.*, 2008 and
89 2011; Castiglioni *et al.*, 2011), Spain (Postigo *et al.*, 2008a, 2008b, 2010 and 2011;
90 Huerta-Fontela *et al.*, 2008a; Boleda *et al.*, 2009), Switzerland (Zuccato *et al.*, 2008;
91 Berset *et al.*, 2010) and the United Kingdom (Kasprzyk-Hordern *et al.*, 2009; Zuccato *et*
92 *al.*, 2008), and also in the USA(Bartelt-Hunt *et al.*, 2009; Chiaia *et al.*, 2008), Australia
93 (Irvine *et al.*, 2011) and Canada (Metcalfé *et al.*, 2010). Trace levels of DAs and their
94 metabolites have also been reported in drinking water (Huerta-Fontela *et al.*, 2008b;
95 Boleda *et al.*, 2009, 2011a and 2011b). However, the occurrence of DAs and their
96 metabolites in groundwater has only been studied in a well water body used as source
97 for abstraction of tap water at a Spanish drinking water treatment plant (DWTP)
98 (Huerta-Fontela *et al.*, 2008b; Boleda *et al.*, 2009, 2011a and 2011b). Hence, to our
99 knowledge, this is the first comprehensive study to specifically address the
100 contamination of aquifers by DAs.

101 The objective of this study was to investigate the occurrence of illicit drugs in an
102 urban aquifer in relation to (1) the spatial distribution of DAs in Barcelona's

103 groundwater, (2) the depth of the groundwater sample, (3) the presence of DAs in
104 recharge sources, and (4) the assessment of the fate of DAs in Barcelona aquifers.

105 To this end, illicit drugs and metabolites belonging to 5 different chemical
106 classes (cocainics, amphetamine-like compounds, opioids, lysergics and cannabinoids)
107 and the prescribed drugs benzodiazepines were analyzed in groundwater samples
108 collected at three sites in the city of Barcelona in May and December 2010.

109

110 **2. SITE DESCRIPTION.**

111 The study area includes Barcelona and part of its metropolitan area in north-
112 eastern Spain. The area is located between the Serra de Collserola (Catalan coastal
113 ranges) and the Mediterranean Sea (Figure 1), both boundaries running approximately
114 NNE–SSW. Other boundaries are constituted by two rivers, the Llobregat (SW) and the
115 Besòs (NE). The climate is typically Mediterranean with an average rainfall of 600 mm
116 per year.

117 Currently, groundwater is used for secondary uses such as streets cleaning and to
118 water plants and public gardens. But it can be considered as an alternative tap water
119 resource since there are several aquifers, characterized by their geological age, below
120 the city (Figure 1). The Palaeozoic aquifer crops out at topographic highs to the NW,
121 which consist of shales and granites. Quaternary aquifers can be found in the rest of the
122 city. In low topographic areas, they are constituted by the alluvial and deltaic sediments
123 of the Llobregat and Besòs rivers. In intermediate areas, they are made up of piedmont
124 cones and coarse alluvial sediments.

125

126 **3. MATERIALS AND METHODS.**

127 **3.1 Sampling.**

128 Thirty-seven water samples were collected during two field campaigns in May
129 2010 (27 samples) and December 2010 (10 samples). One sample was obtained from
130 the River Besòs and thirty-six samples were collected from groundwater: 27 from
131 observation piezometers and 9 from pumping wells. The location of the wells and the
132 piezometers and the screen depths are displayed in Figure 1. Samples were collected in
133 three different zones of the study area: (1) along Mallorca Street (MS) midway between
134 the Collserola Range and the sea (a prosperous part of the city); (2) Poble Sec (PS), on
135 the hillslope of Montjuich representing a less prosperous neighbourhood; and (3) Besòs
136 River Delta (BRD), where groundwater comes mainly from the river. All the

137 groundwater samples were obtained after pumping a volume of at least three times that
138 of the piezometer. Field parameters measured in situ included electric conductivity, pH,
139 temperature, Eh (also called redox potential) and dissolved oxygen. Water samples for
140 drug analysis were measured continuously using a flow cell to avoid contact with the
141 air. The instruments were calibrated daily by means of standard solutions. Samples were
142 collected after stabilization of field parameters and were not filtered in the field. Instead,
143 they were stored in a field refrigerator and taken to the laboratory at the end of the
144 sampling day. Drug samples were stored in polyethylene terephthalate (PET) containers
145 that were amber in colour to avoid photo degradation.

146

147 **3.2 Target drug analytes**

148 A total of 21 drugs and metabolites were analyzed. They belong to 6 different
149 chemical classes: cocaine, cannabinoids, opioids, amphetamine-like compounds,
150 lysergic compounds and benzodiazepines (Table 1). The investigated cocaine
151 compounds were cocaine (CO), its major metabolite benzoylecgonine (BE), and
152 cocaethylene (CE), a product formed when cocaine and ethanol are consumed
153 simultaneously. The target cannabinoids constituted the main psychoactive component
154 of the cannabis plant, Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (THC), cannabinol (CBN), cannabidiol
155 (CBD), and the two metabolic by-products 11-nor-9-carboxy- Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol
156 (THC-COOH) and 11-hydroxy- Δ^9 -tetrahydrocannabinol (OH-THC). Opioids surveyed
157 were morphine (MOR), heroin (HER), the heroin metabolic product 6-acetylmorphine
158 (6ACM), the opioid-agonist methadone (METH), and its main excretion product 2-
159 ethylidene-1,5-dimethyl-3,3-diphenylpyrrolidine (EDDP). The group of amphetamine-
160 like compounds investigated included amphetamine (AM), methamphetamine (MA),
161 3,4-methylenedioxyamphetamine (MDMA or ecstasy), and ephedrine (EPH). The
162 lysergic compound studied was the most potent known hallucinogenic substance,
163 lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD). Benzodiazepines included alprazolam (ALP),
164 diazepam (DIA) and lorazepam (LOR).

165

166 **3.3 Analytical methods.**

167 Water samples collected in May and December 2010 were analyzed for general
168 physical-chemical parameters at the ATLL (Aigües Ter Llobregat) laboratory and at the
169 AMB (Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona) laboratory, respectively.

170 Analysis of the target drugs and metabolites in the collected groundwater samples was
171 carried out by on-line solid-phase extraction (SPE)-liquid chromatography-electrospray-
172 tandem mass spectrometry (SPE-LC-ESI-MS/MS) following a methodology previously
173 described by the authors for analysis of wastewaters (Postigo *et al.*, 2008b and 2011),
174 readily adapted and validated for the present study to the analysis of groundwater
175 matrices. In this method, samples (spiked with deuterated surrogate standards), aqueous
176 calibrations solutions and blanks are analysed in a fully automated way with the aid of a
177 Symbiosis-Pico system (Spark Holland, Emmen, The Netherlands) coupled on-line with
178 the LC-MS/MS system. Samples (5 mL) are preconcentrated onto previously
179 conditioned polymeric PLRPs cartridges (Spark Holland), and after washing of the
180 cartridges with HPLC water, the retained compounds are eluted to the LC-MS/MS
181 system with the chromatographic mobile phase, which consists of gradient
182 acetonitrile/water modified with ammonium formate/formic acid. Chromatographic
183 separation is carried out in a Purospher Star RP-18 end-capped column (125 x 2 mm,
184 particle size 5 µm) and detection is performed in positive ion (PI) mode recording two
185 selected reaction monitoring (SRM) transitions per analyte. Quantitation, based on peak
186 areas, is carried out by the isotope dilution method. This method allows the
187 determination of the compounds at concentrations between 0.4-9.2 ng/L (i.e., the
188 method quantitation limits) and 500 ng/L, with satisfactory precision (relative standard
189 deviations lower than 15 %) and accuracy (absolute recoveries above 80%) for most
190 compounds.

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192 **4. RESULTS OF DAs IN THE URBAN GROUNDWATER OF BARCELONA.**

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194 The average concentration and the maximum levels of the target drugs and metabolites
195 measured in the groundwater samples and their detection frequency are summarized in
196 Table 1a. Figure 2 shows the measured concentrations. No groundwater sample
197 contained all the target compounds and no compound was present in all samples. Ten
198 out of the 21 target compounds, namely, all 5 cannabinoids, LSD, HER, 6ACM, AM,
199 and MA, were not detected in any sample. The most commonly detected drugs were
200 METH, MDMA (or ecstasy) and EDDP (methadone metabolite), with detection
201 frequencies of 86 %, 64 %, 45 %, respectively. DIA and CO were detected in between
202 30 % and 40 % of the samples; and the remaining compounds, namely, CE, MOR, EPH,

203 and the benzodiazepines ALP and LOR, were detected in less than 20 % of the samples.
204 The highest concentrations corresponded to METH (68.3 ng/L at SAP-4) and CO (60.2
205 ng/L at GRA-2).

206 The study area was divided into the three aforementioned zones (Zi). The DAs
207 varied radically from one zone to another in terms of both concentrations and
208 compounds detected (Table 1b). The results are given below.

209 **Z1: MS**

210 In the ten groundwater samples collected along MS (Z1), the compounds
211 identified, ordered by decreasing frequency of detection, were
212 METH>CO>EDDP>BE> MDMA>CE=EPH=DIA. Despite the fact that the ubiquity of
213 METH was greater than that of cocainic compounds, it was present in groundwater at
214 very low concentrations, on average 0.7 ng/L.

215 The highest levels were detected for two cocainic compounds, CO (ranging from
216 50 to 60 ng/L) and its major metabolite BE (ranging from 11 to 16 ng/L) at sampling
217 points GRA-1 and GRA-2, respectively, where CO levels were higher than BE levels.
218 This also occurred at sampling points GRA-3, MODEL, ACO-1, ACO-2 and SL-17 but
219 at a lower concentration for both compounds (Figure 3). This finding contrasts with the
220 concentrations reported in the literature where BE is higher than CO in surface and
221 sewage waters (Table 2). CE, another metabolite of CO, was detected in one sample.

222 **Z2 : PS**

223 Poble Sec was the area with the fewest drugs found in groundwater samples. The
224 most commonly detected drug was METH (10 out of 13 samples) but the highest
225 concentrations corresponded to the amphetamine-like compound MDMA (or ecstasy)
226 detected at an average level of 2.2 ng/L. CO and EDDP were also found, but in less than
227 25% of the groundwater samples with an average concentration of 0.4 ng/L and 0.1
228 ng/L, respectively.

229 **Z3 : BRD**

230 Since the River Besòs contains a large proportion of effluents from secondary
231 WWTPs, a wide range of DAs were detected both in the river and in groundwater
232 samples. The compounds identified in descending order were MDMA=DIA>METH>
233 EDDP>ALP=LOR>MOR>EPH=BE. In contrast to Z1, cocainic compounds were
234 absent (CO and CE) or found only in two samples (BE). MDMA was frequently
235 detected at an average concentration of 8.4 ng/L but EPH was also found in 15% of the
236 samples. DIA was present in all the samples collected and did not vary significantly in

237 the aquifer, ranging from 12.9 to 19.4 ng/L. However, ALP and LOR were less common
238 whereas ALP levels remained practically constant, 2.3 ng/L on average. LOR levels
239 were significantly different, ranging from 1.6 to 39.7 ng/L. As in Z1 and Z2, METH and
240 its metabolite EDDP, were commonly detected. METH levels were especially high in
241 shallow piezometers near the river (between 53 and 68 ng/L) but were insignificant in
242 the deep piezometers located at the same distance from the river. MOR was only found
243 in 20 % of the samples near the river, with an average concentration of 3.8 ng/L.

244

245 **5. DISCUSSION**

246 **5.1 Spatial distribution of DAs in the groundwater samples.**

247 In view of the results of DAs in the three zones studied, it seems clear that drug
248 consumption varies according to the district and is related to social status. CO is an
249 expensive drug that was mainly detected in Z1, which is a more affluent district with
250 several nightclubs. By contrast, Z2 is a less affluent area, in which the main drug
251 detected was MDMA (or ecstasy), cheaper than CO which was detected in only two
252 samples. In Z3, which is a popular area, a mixture of DAs was found because the main
253 contribution to groundwater recharge is the river. As in Z2, the most commonly
254 detected drug was MDMA. Although it would be interesting to define the relationship
255 between drug consumption and affluence, our observations are restricted to the levels
256 and zones in the study area.

257

258 **5.2. DAs profile according to groundwater depth**

259 The concentrations of most DAs decreased with the screen depth of the
260 piezometer, which suggests either some kinetically controlled removal process, as
261 residence time generally increases with depth, or an increasing proportion of water from
262 the Collserola range. This trend was evident at the piezometers in the three zones. The
263 most significant exception took place for cocainic compounds in Z1. As for CO and BE
264 in Z1, the deeper the piezometer, the higher the concentration (Figure 3) for some
265 multilayered piezometers (Figure 1), grouped as follows: (1) GRA-1, GRA-2 and GRA-
266 3, (2) ACO-1 and ACO-2 and (3) SL-17 and SO-30. There is no easy explanation for
267 these levels given that only a small percentage of a CO dose in humans is excreted in
268 urine as the parent drug (5%), whereas a large amount is excreted as BE (45 %) (Baselt,
269 2004). Moreover, the high levels of CO and BE detected at piezometers GRA-1 and
270 GRA-2 could indicate that an accidental or intentional disposal of CO occurred at a

271 specific site (Zuccato et al., 2005). This is supported by the proximity of a high school
272 and a police station to these sampling points.

273

274 **5.3 DAs in recharge sources**

275 **5.3.1. Identification of the potential sources of recharge.**

276 Several recharge sources have been identified in the aquifers of Barcelona
277 (Vazquez-Suñe *et al.*, 2010). Direct rainfall recharge occurs in the non-urbanized areas
278 in the Collserola Range. Seawater intrusion and water from the heavily polluted River
279 Besòs must be considered potential recharge sources in low areas. Additional sources of
280 groundwater recharge can be attributed to anthropogenic activities related to city
281 development including loss from the water supply network. Barcelona is supplied with
282 water from the Ter and Llobregat rivers. This gives rise to a division of the city into two
283 zones with a different water quality and hence two different chemical compositions can
284 be found in waste water. Finally, in paved areas, runoff water washes the road and
285 atmospheric deposition, and recharges the aquifers through direct infiltration or sewer
286 loss. To summarize, up to eight different recharge sources in Barcelona were identified:
287 (1) River Besòs (RIV), (2) rainfall recharge in northern non urban area (R_R), (3) Ter
288 river water supply (TER), (4) Llobregat river water supply (LLOB), (5) Ter river
289 sewage water (SW_T), (6) Llobregat river sewage water (SW_LL), (7) City runoff
290 (RUNOFF), and (8) Sea water intrusion (SEA).

291 To compute the mixing ratios of these end-members in groundwater samples the
292 approach of Carrera *et al.*, (2004) was used. This methodology identifies mixing ratios
293 in the case of uncertain end-members using the concentration of mixed samples to
294 reduce the uncertainty, assuming that the samples are a mixing of the end-members in
295 an unknown proportion. The spatial distribution of the mixing ratios is illustrated in
296 Figure 4. According to the identified sources, in Z1 the main contributor to the total
297 recharge was R_R (60%), especially in the deepest piezometers such as ACOPIO-1 and
298 GRA-2, followed by the sewage network loss (31%) and water supply network loss
299 (9%). In Z2, the main contributors were network sewage (SW_LL) and water supply
300 loss (LL), accounting for 96 %. The remaining 4% corresponded to R_R. As for Z3,
301 RIV (River Besòs) was by far the largest contributor to the total recharge, representing
302 91%. Other contributors to the recharge were network sewage (SW _T) and water
303 supply loss (T). When considering the 3 zones as a whole, the average proportions of
304 the contributors were the following: 21% from water supply network loss, 28% from

305 sewage network loss, 18% due to infiltration in non-urbanized areas and 33% from the
306 River Besòs.

307

308 **5.3.2 DAs levels reported in recharge sources.**

309 The occurrence of the DAs in some of the aforementioned recharge sources has
310 been widely reported in the literature. Concentrations for NE Spain are summarized in
311 Table 2. Cocainic compounds are the most ubiquitous and abundant compounds in the
312 influents of the WWTP, especially BE, which reaches levels exceeding 7 µg/L. Some
313 studies have also confirmed the ubiquity of the opioids MOR, METH and EDDP at
314 relevant levels (ng/L range) in sewage influent. However, HER and 6ACM are seldom
315 or not detected. Amphetamine-like compounds are found at comparatively lower
316 concentrations than cocainics with maximum concentrations of 688 ng/L AM, 277
317 ng/L MA, 598 ng/L MDMA and 591.9 ng/L EPH. The other compounds such as
318 lysergic, cannabinoids and benzodiazepines have been less studied and are found
319 at relatively low concentrations.

320 Little research has been done on the occurrence of DAs in tap waters. Only the
321 cocainics CO and BE and the opioids METH and EDDP have been detected in finished
322 waters of a DWTP and at very low trace levels (Boleda *et al.*, 2011a, 2011b and 2009
323 and Huerta-Fontela *et al.*, 2008b) (table 2).

324 Another recharge source is the River Besòs, but, unfortunately, there are no data
325 concerning DAs. We only have one sample from this river but we fear it may not be
326 representative because the Besòs flow regime, like other Mediterranean rivers, is
327 characterized by its variability, which is controlled by rainfall. However, the River
328 Besòs shares some similarities with the River Llobregat, which has been the subject of
329 many studies (Table 2). Both rivers undergo anthropogenic pressure, receiving
330 extensive urban and industrial wastewater discharges. Consequently, the presence of the
331 DAs can be expected at similar levels. The highest concentrations reported correspond
332 to cocainic compounds, BE and CO, ranging from 15 to 150 ng/L and from 0.4 to 60
333 ng/L, respectively. CE has been found at very low concentrations. The opioids present
334 are MOR, METH and EDDP. METH is commonly present at lower levels than its
335 metabolite EDDP. HER and 6ACM have not been detected. Amphetamine-like
336 compounds have been frequently detected in the Llobregat. MA is present at
337 concentrations lower than those of AM and MDMA, ranging from 0.4 to 50 ng/L.
338 Levels of EPH have only been reported in one study at concentrations of up to 18 ng/L.

339 Cannabinoids and lysergics are absent or found at very low concentrations.
340 Benzodiazepine levels vary considerably between LOR and DIA, with maximum
341 concentrations of 31.5 and 5 ng/L, respectively. ALP has not been detected in surface
342 waters. Overall, as shown in Table 2, concentrations of DAs in surface waters are, on
343 average, one or two orders of magnitude lower than in WWTP influents.

344 Given the high variability of flow rate and the water quality of the River Besòs
345 and the relatively low residence time at the aquifer, it is not sufficient to consider only
346 one end-member from the River Besòs. Instead, three were used to account for the
347 temporal variability. To this end, since only one sample of the DAs in the River Besòs
348 was available, we calculated the concentration of DAs in these river end-members with
349 the river flow using a dilution factor (f) that is calculated as follows:

$$350 \qquad \qquad \qquad f = Q_s / Q_{em} \qquad \qquad \qquad (1)$$

351

352 where Q_s is the flow rate on the day of sampling and Q_{em} is the flow rate of the
353 aforementioned end-members.

354 The adopted DAs concentrations for all sources are shown in table 3.

355

356 **5.4 Assessment of the fate of DAs in Barcelona aquifers.**

357 Once the mixing ratios were assessed and the levels of DAs in the potential
358 recharge source were determined, it was possible to assess the fate of DAs in the
359 aquifer.

360

361 **Z1: MS**

362 Only the most commonly detected compounds along Mallorca Street are
363 discussed in this study (CO, BE, METH and EDDP). These compounds behaved
364 similarly (Figure 5). Estimated concentrations were higher than the measured ones,
365 suggesting the occurrence of removal processes that depleted DAs in groundwater. The
366 presence of species such as nitrate and the levels of dissolved oxygen indicate oxidizing
367 conditions in this zone. Moreover, organic carbon is depleted, which indicates redox
368 processes and suggests degradation of DAs. Regardless of the actual removal process,
369 Figure 5 shows a dramatic reduction in the aquifer concentrations compared with that
370 derived from simple mixing.

371

372 **Z2: PS**

373 As in Z1, only the most commonly detected compounds, which were METH,
374 EDDP, MDMA and CO, are discussed. Sewage water is the main recharge source that
375 contributed to the presence of DAs in the groundwater. But, again, the measured
376 concentrations were much lower than the ones estimated from mixing ratios, which
377 were the ones that should have been obtained from simple mixing (Figure 5). This
378 observation lends support to the view that DAs are susceptible to chemical processes
379 that result in their removal. As in Z1, oxidizing species and the absence of ammonium
380 indicate oxidizing conditions.

381

382 **Z3: BRD**

383 Figure 5 plots the measured and estimated concentrations for BE, MOR, METH,
384 EDDP, MDMA, EPH, DIA and LOR. All DAs, except DIA, behave in a similar way.
385 They are significantly depleted in the aquifer, suggesting again removal processes.
386 Biodegradation, adsorption and mixing processes can reduce DAs levels when river
387 water infiltrates the aquifer. Only DIA levels fall close to the 1:1 line, indicating that
388 DIA was less affected than the other DAs by removal processes and that concentration
389 at the source may be higher than the assumed ones.

390

391 **6. CONCLUSIONS**

392 Groundwater in Barcelona aquifers contains DAs in low but measurable concentrations.
393 The following conclusions may be drawn from this study:

- 394 (1) The most commonly detected drugs were CO, BE, METH, EDDP, MDMA, DIA,
395 MOR, EPH, DIA and LOR, depending on the zone.
- 396 (2) The identified drugs appear to reflect distinct consumption patterns in the different
397 areas and an intentional or accidental disposal of drugs in some cases. Cocainic
398 compounds display higher concentrations in affluent districts whereas MDMA is the
399 dominant drug in less prosperous neighbourhoods.
- 400 (3) Concentrations in the aquifer were generally much lower than those expected due to
401 dilution, as calculated from the mixing ratios of the recharge sources. This suggests
402 significant removal of DAs in the aquifer.
- 403 (4) These results, together with the limited sorption capacity of the sediments, suggest
404 the degradation of DAs in the aquifer under different redox conditions: oxidizing
405 conditions in Z1 and Z2 and reducing conditions in Z3.

406

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408

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574 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

575 **Figure 1.** On the left, schematic description of the hydrogeology of Barcelona: (1a)
576 Llobregat Delta made up of gravels, sands, silts and clays (Holocene, Quaternary), (1b)
577 Besòs Delta composed of gravels, sands, silts and clays (Holocene, Quaternary), (1c)
578 Barcelona Plain consisting of carbonated clays (Pleistocene, Quaternary), (2)
579 Barcelona Plain made up of marls, sandstones and sands (Tertiary) and (3) Collserola
580 Range consisting of shale and granites (Palaeozoic). On the right, a piezometric map of
581 the study zone, which is divided into three zones: (Z1) MS, (Z2) PS and (Z3) BRD. The
582 contour intervals are 2 m (continuous purple line), for heads ranging from 5 to below 25
583 m (continuous blue line) and 25 m above (continuous black line). At the bottom,
584 observation points on each zone, including the depth of the screen :(u) upper, (m)
585 middle, (l) lower and (a) totally screened.

586 **Figure 2.** DAs (drugs of abuse) levels (ng/L) at the three sites: (Z1) MS, (Z2) PS and
587 (Z3) BRD.

588 **Figure 3.**CO (circles) and BE (triangles) levels (ng/L) for some multilayered
589 piezometers at Z1. In black: GRA-1, GRA 2 and GRA-3, dark grey: ACO-1 and ACO-2
590 and light grey: SO-30 and SL-17.

591 **Figure 4.** Mixing ratios evaluated at 36 wells accounting for 6 recharge sources. Note
592 the average concentrations of each zone (Z1, Z2 and Z3) and a detailed scheme of each
593 zone.

594 **Figure 5.** Measured concentrations of DAs in (Z1) MS, (Z2) PS and (Z3) BRD versus
595 the concentration estimated from the end-members (squares) with the mixing ratios of
596 figure 4. Note that measured concentrations are consistently much lower than expected.
597 Note also that none of DAs behave conservatively and only the drugs that are
598 representative of each zone are plotted.

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608 **TABLES**

609 **Table 1.** Frequency of detection (%) and average and maximum concentration (ng/L) of
610 drugs and metabolites measured in **(1a)** Barcelona urban groundwater and **(1b)** detailed
611 in each zone of the study area (MS, PS and BRD).

612 **Table 2.** Occurrence of DAs in tap water, influents and effluents of wastewater
613 treatment plants (WWTP) and in surface waters (River Llobregat). LOD = limit of
614 detection; LOQ = limit of quantification; n.d. = non detected; ^a Average concentration \pm
615 standard deviation; ^b Sample collected at Molins de Rei; ^c Sample collected at St Joan
616 d'Espí. References: ¹ Boleda et al., 2011a; ² Boleda et al., 2011b; ³ Huerta-Fontela et al.,
617 2008b; ⁴ Boleda et al., 2009; ⁵ Huerta-Fontela et al., 2011; ⁶ Huerta-Fontela et al., 2007;
618 ⁷ Huerta-Fontela et al., 2008a; ⁸ Postigo et al., 2008b; ⁹ Boleda et al.,2007 ; ¹⁰ Huerta-
619 Fontela et al.,2010 and ¹¹ Köck-Schulmeyer et al., 2011.

620 **Table 3.** Levels of DAs in the recharge sources expressed in ng/L. “- “: Not included in
621 the analysis. W1: wet period; D1 and D2: dry periods.

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642 **FIGURES**

643 **Figure 1.**

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678 **Figure 2.**

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714 **Figure 3.**

750 **Figura 4.**

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783 **Figure 5.**

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819 **TABLES**820 **Table 1.**821 **Table 1a**

CHEMICAL CLASS	ANALYTE	FREQUENCY OF DETECTION (%) n=36	CONCENTRATION (ng/L)	
			AVERAGE ± STD	MAX
COCAINICS	CO	31	3.8±12.8	60.2
	BE	19	1.5±4.5	19.6
	CE	3	0.05±0.3	1.8
CANNABINOIDS	THC	0	-	-
	CBN	0	-	-
	CBD	0	-	-
	THC-COOH	0	-	-
OPIOIDS	OH-THC	0	-	-
	MOR	8	1.4±5.2	27.2
	HER	0	-	-
	6ACM	0	-	-
	METH	86	7.4±15.3	68.3
AMPHETAMINE LIKE COMPOUNDS	EDDP	44	0.7±1.7	8.2
	AM	0	-	-
	MA	0	-	-
LYSERGIC COMPOUNDS BENZODIAZEPINES	MDMA	64	3.9±6.6	36.8
	EPH	8	0.3±1.3	7.3
	LSD	0	-	-
	DIA	39	5.9±7.9	19.4
	ALP	14	0.8±2.1	6.4
	LOR	14	3.1±9.1	39.7

835 **Table 1b**836 **Z1. MS**

CHEMICAL CLASS	ANALYTE	FREQUENCY OF DETECTION (%) n=10	CONCENTRATION (ng/L)	
			AVERAGE ± STD	MAX
COCAINICS	CO	90	13.1±22.5	60.2
	BE	50	3.2±5.7	16.3
	CE	10	0.2±0.6	1.8
OPIOIDS	METH	100	0.7±1.1	3.8
	EDDP	60	0.8±1.9	6.1
AMPHETAMINE LIKE COMPOUNDS	MDMA	20	0.2±0.4	1.2
	EPH	10	0.02±0.06	0.2
BENZODIAZEPINES	DIA	10	0.3±0.9	2.9

842 **Z2. PS**

CHEMICAL CLASS	ANALYTE	FREQUENCY OF DETECTION (%) n=13	CONCENTRATION (ng/L)	
			AVERAGE ± STD	MAX
COCAINICS	CO	15	0.4±0.9	2.5
OPIOIDS	METH	77	0.3±0.3	1.2
	EDDP	23	0.1±0.3	1.0
AMPHETAMINE LIKE COMPOUNDS	MDMA	62	2.2±2.1	6.4

847 **Z3. BDR**

CHEMICAL CLASS	ANALYTE	FREQUENCY OF DETECTION (%) n=13	CONCENTRATION (ng/L)		
			AVERAGE ± STD	MAX	River Besòs
COCAINICS	BE	15	1.6±5.4	19.6	42
OPIOIDS	MOR	23	3.8±8.3	27.2	0
	METH	85	19.6±20.7	68.3	12
	EDDP	69	1.2±2.2	8.17	23
	MDMA	100	8.4±9.3	36.8	5.8
AMPHETAMINE LIKE COMPOUNDS	EPH	15	0.8±2.2	7.29	78
BENZODIAZEPINES	DIA	100	16.2±1.8	19.4	4.1
	ALP	38	2.3±3	6.38	0
	LOR	38	8.5±13.9	39.7	25

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855 **Table 2.**

856	DRUGS OF ABUSE	WWTPs			SURFACE WATERS	
		TAP WATERS	Influent			Effluent
			Concentration (ng/L)	Concentration (ng/L)		
857		Average/Range	Average/Range	Average/Range	Average/Range	
858	COCAINICS					
859	CO	<LOD ¹ 0.4 ²	79 ⁶ 4-4700 ⁷ 860.9±213.6 ^{a,8}	17 ⁶ 1-100 ⁷ 6.2±3.7 ^{a,8}	6 ⁵ 0.1±0.0 ^{a,3} 40±5 ^{a,3} 9±2 ^{a,3} 60±10 ^{a,3} 10±4 ^{a,3} 12.9±11.7 ^{a,b,11} 4.6±1.2 ^{a,c,11} 0.4-1.6 ¹ 77 ⁶	
860						
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862	BE	45 ³ <LOD-1.5 ¹ 0.4 ²	810 ⁶ 0.1-7500 ⁷ 4225.7±1142.8 ^{a,8}	216 ⁶ 1-1500 ⁷ 30.3±17.6 ^{a,8}	15±1 ^{a,3} 70±25 ^{a,3} 35±10 ^{a,3} 150±60 ^{a,3} 50±12 ^{a,3} 36.7±13.9 ^{a,b,11} 33.6±3.7 ^{a,c,11} 14.6-20.1 ¹ 0.15±0.15 ^a	
863						
864						
865	CE	0.2 ²	77.5±33.2 ^{a,8}	1.7±1.2 ^{a,8}		
866	OPIOIDS					
867	MOR		44±34.5 ^{a,9} 162.9±20 ^{a,8} 25.5-278 ⁴	22.5±33.6 ^{a,9} 21.8±3.0 ^{a,8} 12-81.1 ⁴	5.5±0.6 ^{a,9} 1.5-12.2 ⁴	
868	METH	0.17-0.85 ⁴ 0.2 ²	12.7±8.9 ^{a,9} 3.4-1531 ⁴	11.4±7.9 ^{a,9} 3.4-732 ⁴	6.4±2.1 ^{a,9} 1.9-9.4 ⁴ 1.7-3 ¹	
869	EDDP	0.62-3.7 ⁴ 0.4 ²	19.7±18.4 ^{a,9} 3.3-1029 ⁴	22.4±23.6 ^{a,9} 2.7-1150 ⁴	12.3±2.8 ^{a,9} 5.2-31.4 ⁴ 7.2-11.8 ¹	
870	6ACM		12.8±3.1 ^{a,8}	3.6±0.5 ^{a,8}		
871	AMPHETAMINES					
872	AM		15 ⁶ 3-688 ⁷ 41.1±9.1 ^{a,8}	<LOQ ⁶ 4-210 ⁷ 0.5±0.1 ^{a,8}	0.94±1 ^{a,9} 0.4±0.0 ^{a,3} 50±5 ^{a,3} 40±10 ^{a,3} 9±3 ^{a,3} 0.4±0.0 ^{a,3} <0.2 ³ 1±0.5 ^{a,3} 1±0.1 ^{a,3} 2±1 ^{a,3} <0.2 ³ 3 ⁹	
873						
874	MA		3-277 ⁷ 18.2±5.8 ^{a,8}	3-90 ⁷ 6.3±0.6 ^{a,8}	1.5±1 ^{a,3} 25±10 ^{a,3} 3±1 ^a 40±5 ^{a,3} 1±0.5 ^{a,3} 0.7±1.2 ^{a,b,11} 7.3±10.4 ^{a,c,11} 0.4-1.3 15.2±5.6 ^{a,b,11} 18.2±4.4 ^{a,c,11}	
875						
876	MDMA		49 ⁶ 2-598 ⁷ 133.6±29.8 ^{a,8}	41 ⁹ 2-267 ⁷ 82.1±22.2 ^{a,8}		
877						
878	EPH		591.9±62.3 ^{a,8}	117.8±17.3 ^{a,8}		
879	CANNABINOIDS					
880	OH-THC		4.3±7.8 ^{a,8}	8.4±3.8 ^{a,8}	5.2±4.1 ^{a,9}	
881	THC		15.7±12.8 ^{a,9} 11.3-127 ⁴	20.5 ⁴	<LOD-12 ⁴	
882	LYSERGIC COMPOUNDS					
883	LSD		2.8±1.2 ^{a,8}	0.3±0.2 ^{a,8}		
884	BENZODIAZEPINES					
885	DIA	<0.4 ⁵	n/d-49 ¹⁰	n/d ¹⁰	3 ⁶ 5 ⁵ 1.2±0.0 ^{a,b,11} 4.8±0.1 ^{a,c,11}	
886	ALP		n/d-4 ¹⁰	n/d-1 ¹⁰		
887	LOR		n/d-502 ¹⁰	n/d-532 ¹⁰	20.1±0.6 ^{a,b,11} 31.5±4.4 ^{a,c,11}	

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890 **Table 3.**

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892	End-members	CO	BE	MOR	METH	EDDP	MDMA	EPH	DIA	LOR
892	W1	-	21.4	2.6	6.4	11.8	3.0	40.2	2.1	13.0
893	Besòs River(RIV)									
	D1	-	131.9	15.8	39.4	72.9	18.3	225.0	12.9	80.1
	D2	-	172.1	20.6	51.5	95.1	23.8	319.0	16.8	104.6
894	Water Supply									
	TER	0.4	0.4	-	0.4	2.5	0	-	-	-
895	LLOB									
896	Sewage water									
	SW_TER	50	500	-	7.5	12	50	-	-	50
	SW_LLOB									
897	Rainfall recharge									
	R_R	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	non-urban									

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